

Can genetic engineering overcome public mistrust by adopting approaches for more democratic governance?

Introduction and key concepts for discussion

In this essay, I will argue for a model which will enhance democratisation of genetic engineering governance. By this we will use Stirling's (2014) definition of democracy as "access by the least powerful to the capacities for challenging power" and by governance we aim to elucidate processes which 'govern' decision-making processes where technological innovations in genetic engineering affect the lives of people across the world.

I want to also use several ideas from Science and Technology Studies (STS) to make some of my arguments throughout the essay, these are as follows:

- Co-productionist view of the world – how we choose to classify, order and interpret the world is also how we choose live in it, moreover, the realms of technological innovations and patterns in society move in the same direction over time, meaning that they are both "co-produced". Thus, our values and approach to genetic engineering limits (or opens up) what is possible and breakthroughs in technology itself also influences our own positions (Jasanoff, 2004).
- Power processes – high value technologies produce power asymmetries throughout history e.g. military hegemony and 5G technology. Societies which embrace and exploit novel technologies usually then set the terms and use of that technology, creating large power asymmetries.
- Knowledge processes – using Foucault's ideas of connecting power-processes and knowledge processes together, typified by the "panopticon", creating an illusion of being observed all the time, and knowledge of this has the power to self-regulate oneself (Foucault, 1977). More broadly, I will be analysing deficits of knowledge processes using Stirling's Incertitude model in order to tease out uncertainty, ambiguity and ignorance (Stirling, 2010).

I will now set the main introductory elements to this essay. The key idea I want to get across is that we should embrace Incertitude as a model to help us better understand the impacts of innovations within the field of genetic engineering, to address knowledge deficits and to acknowledge the power and values-laden processes at play, this will help us navigate uncertainty in the future of genetic engineering.

Blanket moratorium on research nor unfettered experimentation will resolve governance issues, instead, increased public participation and democratic engagement is needed to direct the trajectory of technological innovations along conscious and deliberate pathways. This will be the second key argument in this essay, that, there exist complex ecologies of participation which support the process of democratising science and technology governance.

Discussion

Governance processes which have not worked

In 1975, the Asilomar Conference was organised by scientists leading to a moratorium on further genetic engineering (GE) research until a code of practice and risk management approaches were in place (Berg, 2008). While this appeared extraordinary and lent credence to scientists' abilities to self-regulate. In reality, it was an exercise of self-preservation in an atmosphere of increasing public mistrust by scientists conducting experiments behind closed doors, specifically, on recombinant DNA technologies, a method which allows one to edit the human genetic code (Jasanoff and Hurlbut, 2018). Berg (2008) asks the question "what are the benefits of allowing researchers to continue to work with recombinant DNA?"; many scientist had predicted a windfall of important drug discoveries and agricultural industrial products – but these have largely not materialised. Instead, what we have is a mistrust of these technologies as encapsulated by the controversies of the alleged designer babies produced by the Chinese scientist He Jiankui in 2018 which have been dismissed by scientists across the globe as "bad- science" (BBC News, 2018).

Therein lies the problem of letting scientists define their own rule book of ethics and code in an insular manner, and dismiss shortcomings as "bad-science" (Wade, 1993, p.497). There needs to be greater responsibility and opening up such governance processes. This is why Berg (2008), one of the original architect of the Asilomar Conference, writes in Nature that it would be difficult to convene another one of these conferences again, he comments that scientists are now more dispersed across more commercial entities. However, he concludes that to overcome the economic-self-interest and irreconcilable challenges held by social values, that we need to get ahead of the curve and have engagement and consultation with the public much earlier on.

Global Observatory for governance

Jasanoff and Hurlbut (2018) appear to agree with Berg's (2008) assessment that another large gathering of scientists would not be helpful to self-regulate, nor does it address governance deficits. Instead they propose a "global observatory" for gene editing be developed - an infrastructure to gather multiple inputs steered by values and priorities in a similar approach to networks and coalitions for human rights and climate change, a sort of 'global clearinghouse'.

Their article asks critical questions about power processes: who is at the discussion table? What power imbalances exist? Who shapes the debate? They refer to a recent 2015 summit which brought together scientists and non-scientists. However, there was little opportunities for deep learning; there were two separate discussions on technical and disruptions of social norms and the two groups did not speak to each other. Thus, they argue for new infrastructure, a global observatory, which can help create a new 'social contract' for Science. This global clearinghouse would report on activities and provide complex knowledge networks to provide consensus approaches for whether to halt research or not.

Bolstering global observatory with Incertitude framework

Let's be slightly controversial here and use a case study to illustrate controversial governance processes, suppose we wanted to understand the trajectories of genetic engineering to produce designer babies, what would that look like?

I have tried to model key controversial questions within the Incertitude framework to demonstrate its potency in addressing controversies from a variety of angles.

INCERTITUDE framework for "Designer Baby"	<i>Outcome known</i>	<i>Outcome Unknown</i>
<i>Probabilities known</i>	RISK <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Selection of recombinant fertilised eggs 	AMBIGUITY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gene mutation e.g. frameshift mutation etc. leading to phenotypical changes
<i>Probabilities unknown</i>	UNCERTAINTY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lifespan reduced (dolly the Sheep) ▪ Who owns genetic patents/licenses? 	IGNORANCE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What make humans human? ▪ What would evolution do if it had another 10 million years?

Table 1: Table adapted from (Stirling, 2010) in order to demonstrate uncertainties in genetic engineering technology with respect to the debate on "designer baby".

What the incertitude framework should demonstrate is the capacity to more broadly discuss technologies that have uncomfortable social values, the aim here is not to exhaustively discuss all the boxes (perhaps something for the 'global observatory' to do), however, to outline a process by which to have these conversations and navigate different elements of knowledge gaps. For instance, we know that the first cloned mammal "Dolly the sheep" had a shorter lifespan than normal (New Scientist, 2003), so we know this as an outcome, however, we do know the probabilities of that in humans, likewise we may know the probabilities of mutations/errors in recombinant DNA gene-editing, however, we have no idea of the phenotypical changes (although the human imagination has projected this thought via various superheroes in popular culture).

Now we move on to the final box – ignorance, where neither probabilities nor outcomes are known. How do we know that humans dictating their own genetic transmission is not part of the natural evolution itself? After all, evolution itself is survival of the fittest and involves elements of selective breeding (Zietman et al., 2010). Stirling (2010) is pointing here to large knowledge deficits, the so called "unknown unknowns", which may be addressed via linkages across diverse knowledge bases.

The main benefit of adopting the Incertitude framework is a more open approach for discussions on particular pathways and ask critical questions such as: how reversible is this trajectory? How flexible, adaptable and modular are the associated downstream changes to avoid "lock-in"? What new knowledges might we learn from deliberately pursuing diverse approaches? (Stirling, 2010).

Web of people mobilised – ecologies of participation

We will now try to synthesise our key concepts into action. For the global observatory, bolstered by the Incertitude framework, to work in practice, we need to articulate how the public are mobilised by “ecologies of participation”. Chilvers et al. (2018) present a model to demonstrate how diverse forms of participation connect with wider systems. Although the model was applied to energy systems in the UK, it has potential for explanatory power in understanding critical transition changes, in our case, to develop more democratic governance principles in genetic engineering technological innovations.

Within the ecologies of participation, three layers are marked out in a relational and systemic manner, grounded, in co-productionist viewpoint (see Table 2).

The first layer of participation involves well-established participation mechanism e.g. from our discussion, the Asilomar conference, these are thus **dominant** norms, the second layer are wider more **diverse** forms of participation that can often be marginalised. We can observe these through protests e.g. against genetically modified (GM) food or organisms (GMO). In genetic engineering, there are wide range of controversies ranging from commercial genetic patenting rights to women’s reproductive rights.

Table 2: Adapted from *Ecologies of participation* (Chilvers et al., 2018, p.205). Three relational layers of participation which form a systemic ecosystem. The bullets are examples of the different types of participation.

Finally, an “**emergent**” layer of participation is unexpected, de-centered and emerging, this has potential to significantly disrupt the existing status quo due to novel forms of participation e.g. hacking, co-design. An example of this is from He Jiankui’s illegal experiment to create the world’s first alleged designer baby (BBC News, 2018), this has re-framed debates and controversies around governance processes.

Critique of discussion and Conclusion

I have demonstrated the practical applicability of the Incertitude framework; however, its use has largely focussed on crisis management. The European Environment Agency's (EEA) research area around the precautionary principle and early warning signs (Harremoës et al., 2002) highlight the tragic preventable damage which have occurred as a result of human actions on the environment, however, the Incertitude framework has yet to be applied to situations where early warning signs are heeded, and thus leading to more proactive models of governance away from crisis management approaches.

An interesting corollary of this discussion is around the precautionary principle in which "preventive action may be taken without waiting for firm scientific evidence" (Spiegelhalter and Riesch, 2011, p.4747). However, this is deeply contested when commercial interests clash with societal values. Who gets to decide when to halt or resume innovative research? This is where the global observatory is a useful approach to gather consensus, and the ecologies of participation provides a description of how different participation processes are related in a systemic manner. Even then, these processes can be manipulated by power processes via selective governance processes, prescriptiveness and framing biases. The main mitigation to overcome these risks is to continue to widen, diversify and deepen the democratisation of science and technology to increase the possibility of the least powerful to effect decision making of the powerful and adapting to local contexts.

The final critique is around the practical applicability of the models discussed. Jasanoff has made some strides in trying to connect technological innovations with some of the deeper elements of human life. In her book, *Reframing Rights: Bioconstitutionalism in the Genetic Age*, Jasanoff (2011) tackles the immediate implications of human gene-editing, grounding the consequences of biotechnological innovation into textual analysis of the Law. She argues that the current period of significant change within life sciences should be seen as Constitutional (Jasanoff, 2011, p.3).

I would argue further still that so much of the rapid rate of technological innovation precedes changes in the Law, usually, the first innovators set the terms and uses of newly exploited technology and the Law responds in a lagging manner. Whereas, I argue, as does Jasanoff, that some of the rapid innovations within life sciences need to go through Constitutional processes to reevaluate what kind of societies we want to live in and what it means to be human, and to avoid dismissing and marginalising controversial issues across fault lines as "bad science".

In conclusion, we should not wait for science and technological innovations to determine our fate. Current discourse is framed around risk management and abstract moral concerns. We need to develop frameworks to include the least powerful to impact decision making. Those with power, should not shy away from controversial topics such as the 'designer baby', instead tackle it head on, only then can we get ahead of the technological frontier by developing frameworks for social values and democratic governance to impact decision making.

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